

DIALECTICAL COMPARISON OF PHONOLOGICAL, LEXICAL, AND SYNTACTIC FEATURES OF KANKANAELY IN ROGUS, CAUAYAN CITY AND IN CAMBALY, BAGULI²

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ABSTRACT

This research compares the phonological, morphological, lexical, and syntactic features of the Kankanaely dialect in Barangay Rogus, Cauayan City, Isabela, and Barangay Cambaly, Bagulin, La Union. The study found similarities and differences in the location of stress in certain words, the use of prefixes to derive verbs and adverbs, and the vocabulary used in each dialect. However, both dialects share the same syntactic structure. These findings contribute to the understanding of dialectal variations in the Kankanaely language and highlight the impact of geographical and social factors on language evolution.

Keywords: *Kankanaely, Dialectical Comparison, Phonology*

INTRODUCTION

Every language has a method of human communication, consisting of words that have undergone formation and are structured conventionally and conveyed by speech, writing, or gesture. Although this is true for all languages, a particular language may show certain features that differ from the rest. This makes the investigation of similarities and differences between languages interesting. Especially similarities and differences between dialects of a certain language.

The Philippines is an archipelago in which many languages are spoken. Just like other languages, Philippine languages exhibit dialects. One language that can be a good subject for dialectal research is Kankanaely. Kankanaely is one of the spoken Languages of Igorot tribes in the Philippines. It refers to both the natives and the language they speak. Aside from Mountain Province, Kankanaelys have migrated to other provinces in the Philippines. Some of them can be found in Barangay Rogus Cauayan City, Isabela, and others in Cambaly, Bagulin La Union.

The Kankanaelys in Rogus, Cauayan City, Isabela came from Cambaly, Bagulin, La Union. The migration occurred under martial law in 1972. Because people easily adapt their actions and their manner of talking to other people that surround them, Kankanaely speakers in Barangay Rogus are somewhat different from those in Cambaly, Bagulin in how they speak, use the Kankanaely language, construct a sentence, and how they express themselves using the Kankanaely dialect. The said phenomenon is what the researchers want to explore.

According to Cabilitazan (2020), Kankanaely is a widely used dialect in the northern region of the Philippines. She explored the development of a corpus for the Kankanaely dialect. Furthermore, the corpus was then used to establish the syntactic rules of Kankanaely.

This study has been undertaken to determine the similarities and differences of phonological, morphological, lexical, and syntactic features of the Kankanaely language in Barangay Rogus, Cauayan City, Isabela, and Cambaly, Bagulin, La Union. Moreover, this research further justifies the existence of the Kankanaely dialects.

METHODS

The researchers employed a qualitative research approach, specifically a descriptive comparative research design, utilizing interviews as the primary elicitation method. This approach was suited to analyzing phonological, morphological, lexical, and syntactic features, facilitating an explanation of the relevant processes and patterns. Two instruments were used to gather data from native Kankanaely speakers: a list of Tagalog words

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presented to participants and a cellphone for conducting and recording interviews. The study involved ten native Kankanaey speakers aged between 20 and 60 years, with five participants from Barangay Rogus, Cauayan City, Isabela, and the other five from Cambaly, Bagulin, and La Union. Prior to data collection, participants signed a consent form detailing the study's purposes, their agreement to participate, and the data needed. Interviews were conducted in Tagalog for clarity, while participants responded in Kankanaey, as the interviewer was also proficient in the language.

The study collected data on Kankanaey's phonological, morphological, lexical, and syntactic features, validated by an expert comparing the dialect's base forms with their English equivalents. Participants translated Kankanaey words into English, pronounced them, and used them in sentences. The interviews were recorded and transcribed for analysis. Data were examined qualitatively, focusing on phonology, morphology, lexicon, and syntax to identify and compare structural similarities and differences between the dialects of Barangay Rogus, Cauayan City, and Barangay Cambaly, Bagulin, La Union.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research compares the Kankanaey dialect at Barangay Rogus, Cauayan City, Isabela, and Barangay Cambaly, Bagulin, and La Union. The research has undergone phonological, morphological, and lexical syntactic analyses. The process has produced the following findings:

Phonological Similarities and Differences

Phonological Similarities

According to Dixon (1977), an Almost extinct language from north-east Queensland prefers each word to consist of a whole number of disyllabic units, either all the form "stressed syllable-unstressed syllable" or else all the form "unstressed syllable-stressed syllable." There is also a rule that shortens a long vowel whenever it falls in an illicit syllable (that is, a syllable that cannot bear stress, in terms of the general constraints on Yidiny phonology).

Table 1. Phonological Similarities between Kankanaey Rogus and Kankanaey Cambaly

VERBS	
First syllable stress	Second syllable stress
[anap] Find	[kŪma'an] Leave
[bŪkat] Open	[aɪ-ajam] Play
[Ūada] Have	
NOUNS	
First syllable stress	Second syllable stress
[dŪontog] Mountain	[be-æ] Home
[pɪ'lak] Money	[makan] Food
	[ka-εŪ] Wood
	[tak'kay] Hand
	[ɪpŪgaŪ] People
	[kagasat'] Destiny
	[na'tey] Dead
PRONOUNS	
First syllable stress	Second syllable stress
[sɪs'a] Him/Her	[sak-ɛn] I
[sɪk-a] You	[na-æ] It
ADJECTIVES	
First syllable stress	Second syllable stress

[bʊŋɔt] Angry

[map'tɛŋ] Beautiful
 [napʊdnɔ] Honest
 [man-atʊŋ] Hot
 [malɪtɛŋ] Cold
 [mam-ɪs] Delicious
 [man-agʊb] Stink
 [maka-aɪ-ayɔ] Attractive
 [narad'sak] Happy

ADVERBS

First syllable stress

[ɪna'gɛʊ] Daily

Second syllable stress

[sak'baɪ] Before

[ʻadaʊɪ] Far

[ma-ɪd] No

DETERMINER

First syllable stress

[ad-ado] A lot of

Second syllable stress

[ɪsallæ] One

CONJUNCTION

First syllable stress

[gapɔ] Because

PREPOSITION

[aglaʊlaʊ] Around

Similarities between the two dialects in terms of stress are revealed. Phonological similarities between Kankanaey in Rogus and Kankanaey in Cambaly occur in the stress of certain verbs, nouns, pronouns, adjectives, adverbs, determiners, conjunctions, and prepositions. Table 1.0 shows that there are similarities between the Kankanaey in Rogus and Cambaly. The similarities are seen in the location of stress in certain verbs, nouns, pronouns, adjectives, adverbs, determiners, conjunctions, and prepositions. Both the Kankanaeys of Rogus and Cambali pronounce the words [anap], [bʊkat], [ʊada], [dʊntɔg], [pɪ'lak], [sɪs'ja], [sɪk-a], [bʊŋɔt], [ɪna'gɛʊ], [ad-ado] and [gapɔ] with stress in the first syllable. Hence, it was found out that out of the sixty-five (65) words on the list of Kankanaey in Rogus and Cambaly, eleven (11) words have stress in the first syllable.

Furthermore, It shows that the words [kʊma'an], [aɪ-ajam], [be-æ], [makan], [ka-ɛʊ], [tak'kay], [ɪpʊgaʊ], [kagasat'], [na'tɛy], [sak-ɛn], [na-æ], [map'tɛŋ], [napʊdnɔ], [man-atʊŋ], [malɪtɛŋ], [mam-ɪs], [man-agʊb], [maka-aɪ-ayɔ], [narad'sak], [sak'baɪ], [ʻadaʊɪ], [ma-ɪd] [ɪsallæ], and [aglaʊlaʊ] are pronounced with a stress in the second syllable. Hence, we found that out of the sixty-five (65) words on the list of Kankanaey in Rogus and Cambaly, twenty-four (24) words have stress in the second syllable. However, both places maintain the existence of the Kankanaey language despite the changing environment and merging of different languages.

Phonological Differences

Phonological differences between Kankanaey in Rogus and Kankanaey in Cambaly are manifested in the location of stress in certain nouns, pronouns, and adverbs. Table 2 shows the differences between the Kankanaey of Barangay Rogus Cauayan City Isabela and Barangay Cambaly, Bagulin La Union. The table reveals that the differences lie in the location of stress among some word categories, such as nouns, pronouns, and adverbs. For nouns, the word [tak'kaɪ] in Rogus is stressed in the second syllable, while [tak'kæ] in Cambaly is in the first syllable. The word [ag'sapa] in Rogus is stressed in the first syllable, while [ag'sapa] in Cambaly is in the second syllable. It can also be observed that the Kankanaey word for hand is pronounced differently.

For pronouns, only one word was seen to have a phonological difference. The Kankanaey for morning [daɪtakʊ] is stressed in the third syllable in Rogus, while [da'ɛtakʊ] in Cambaly is stressed in the second syllable. In addition, the said word has different vowel sounds in the two dialects.

Table 2. Phonological Differences between Kankanaey Rogus and Kankanaey Cambaly

Nouns

Rogus [tak'kaɪ] Hand [ag'sapa] Morning	Cambali [tak'kæ] Hand [ag'sapa] Morning
Pronoun	
[daɪtakʊ] We	[da'etakʊ] We
Adverb/Adjective	
['adaʊɪ] Far	['adaʊɪ] Far

For adverbs, only one word demonstrates the phonological difference. The Kankanaey for far is pronounced in Rogus with a stress on the third syllable, while the same is pronounced in Cambaly with a stress on the second syllable.

On the one hand, the changes in Kankanaey in Barangay Rogus, Cauayan City, Isabela resulted from the exposure of the Kankanaeys in the said place to Ilocano. Because they were surrounded by Ilocanos, the Kankanaeys preferred to use Ilocano, hence the changes in accent. In other words, the Ilocano language influenced certain Kankanaey words. On the other hand, Kankanaey in Cambaly, Bagulin, and La Union maintained the original accent because they often used the said language and passed it without changes to the next generation.

The foregoing phenomenon is underscored by Sofu (2009). He indicated that patterns of language use in a family and the attitudes of family members towards heritage language or the language of the wilder community are also important determining factors. The results show that shift or maintenance takes different directions within three generations because of mostly outside factors shaping the attitude of bilingual speakers.

Moreover, phonological differences demonstrate that their intonation has different but the same meaning with a different accent because the accent at Barangay Rogus was mixed with the Ilocano dialect while the accent at Cambaly is from Cordillera which is the origin place of the Kankanaey native speakers. Some words have different stress but the same meaning. For the Kankanaey speakers in Rogus, the stress of the words is missing because some of them have not learned how to pronounce them correctly. But in Bagulin, they are fluent in speaking the Kankanaey language. From Cambaly, the tone of pronouncing each of the words has more power than Rogus's accent.

Morphological Similarities And Differences

Morphological Similarities

In this paper, we have introduced an enhanced root-based algorithm that handles the problems of affixes, including prefixes, suffixes, and infixes, depending on the morphological pattern of the word. **According to** Ghwanmeh (2009), the stemming concept has been used to eliminate all kinds of affixes, including infixes. A series of simulation experiments have been conducted to test the performance of the proposed algorithm.

Table 3 shows the derivation of certain verbs in Kankanaey both in Rogus and in Cambaly. The derivation shows that the prefixes "**MAN**," "**NAN**," "**MA**," and "**NA**" are placed at the beginning of the root word or base form to produce another form of Kankanaey verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. The table further shows that the prefix "**MAN**" is used to indicate present tense, while prefixes "**NAN**," "**MA**," and "**NA**" are used to indicate past tense.

Table 3. The use of MAN, NAN, and MA, NA

VERBS	
MAN + free morphemes=Kankanaey verbs	NAN + free morphemes=Kankanaey verbs
Man + ibil = Man-ibil (Umiyak) (Cry)	Nan + ibil = Nan-ibil (Umiyak) (Cried)
Man + uga = Man-uga (Umiyak) (Cry)	Nan + uga = Nan-uga (Umiyak) (Cried)

Man + daus = Mandaus (Maglinis) (Clean)	Nan + daus = Nandaus (Naglinis) (Cleaned)
Man + linis = Manlinis (Maglinis) (Clean)	Nan + linis = Nanlinis (Naglinis) (Cleaned)
Man + ammeng = Man-ammeng (Tumawa) (Laugh)	Nan + ammeng = Nan-ammeng (Tumawa) (Laughed)
Man + siyek = Mansiyek (Tumawa) (Laugh)	Nan + siyek = Nansiyek (Tumawa) (Laughed)
Man + kansyon = Mankansyon (Kumanta) (Sing)	Nan + kansyon = Nankansyon (Kumanta) (Sung)
Man + kanta = Mankanta (Kumanta) (Sing)	Nan + kanta = Nankanta (Kumanta) (Sung)
Man + anap = Man-anap (Maghanap) (Find)	Nan + anap = Nan-anap (Naghanap) (Found)
Man + ay-ayam = Man-ay-ayam (Maglaro) (Play)	Nan + ay-ayam = Nan-ay-ayam (Naglaro) (Played)
Man + abel = Man-abel (Maghabi) (Weave)	
Man + dait = Mandait (Maghabi) (Weave)	
MA + free morphemes=Kankanaey verbs	
Ma + nagtag = Managtag (Tumakbo) (Run)	

ADJECTIVES

MAN + free morphemes=Kankanaey adjectives	MA + free morphemes=Kankanaey adjectives
Man + atung = Man-ating (Mainit) (Hot)	Ma + liteng = Maliteng (Malamig) (Cold)
Man + atong = Man-atong (Mainit) (Hot)	Ma + kaay-ayo = Makaay-ayo (Kaakit-kit) (Attractive)
Man + layad = Manlayad (Galak) (Glad)	NA + free morphemes=Kankanaey adjectives
Man + agub = Man-agub (Mabaho) (Stink)	Na + audio = Napudno (Tapat) (Honest)
Man + bungot = Manbungot (Magalit) (Angry)	Na + radsak = Naradsak (Masaya) (Happy)

ADVERBS

NA + free morphemes=Kankanaey adverbs

Na + paspas = Napaspas
 (Mabilis)
 (Fast)
 Na + partak = Napartak
 (Mabilis)
 (Fast)
 Na + ligat = Naligat
 (Mahirap)
 (Hard)

Although the shown derivations exhibit similarities, if observed, there are few differences. For instance, the word (ibid), when they use it in their conversations, becomes man-ibid. Similarly, uga becomes man-uga, daus becomes man-daus, and linis becomes man-linis. Among adjectives, some words are formed with the prefix MAN to indicate the present tense. For example, the word (atung) becomes man-atung, layad to man-layad, agub to man-agub, bungot to man-bungot. Again, the idea of Sofu (2009) mentioned earlier applies in this case.

Morphological Differences

Table 4 shows the morphological difference between Kankanaey in Rogus and Kankanaey in Cambaly. The differences lie in the use of certain prefixes in deriving verbs. The prefixes "LU," "LIN," and "NA" that derive certain verbs in Barangay Rogus have the prefix counterparts "PU," "PIN," and "TIN" in Cambaly. This finding implies that the change occurs on the initial sound "l" instead of "p" and "n" instead of "t."

Table 4. Morphological differences between Kankanaey in Rogus and Kankanaey in Cambaly

VERBS	
LU + free morphemes = Kankanaey verbs	PU + free morphemes = Kankanaey verbs
Lu + magto = Lumagto (Jump) (Tumalon)	Pu + madtok = Pumadtok (Jump) (Pumadtok)
LIN + free morphemes = Kankanaey verbs	PIN + free morphemes = Kankanaey verbs
Lin + magto = Linmagto (Jumped) (Tumalon)	Pin + madtok = Pinmadtok (Jumped) (Tumalon)
NA + free morphemes = Kankanaey verbs	TIN + free morphemes = Kankanaey verbs
Na + nagtag = Nanagtag (Ran) (Tumakbo)	Tin + magtag = Tinmagtag (Ran) (Tumakbo)

According to Kamwangamalu (2003), studies of social change and language maintenance and shift have tended to focus on minority immigrant languages. Very little is known about the language shift from a demographically dominant language to a minority but economically dominant one, and he said because they don't use the Kankanaey language every day, they forget they must think about his translation for a few minutes before they remember and maybe because they were old, and it had been a long time since they moved to barangay Rogus.

Lexical Similarities And Differences

Lexical Similarities

Table 5 shows the categories of words that are usually similar in Kankanaey Rogus and Kankanaey Cambaly. Certain words under verbs and adjectives are similar in both places. The verbs "anap" or find and "ay-ayam" or play are words that have the same meaning and are used in both places. The table also shows that the adjectives layad for (glad), agub for (stink), bungot for (angry), liteng for (cold), ka-ay ayo for (attractive), pudno for (honest), and radsak for (happy) are also used by Kankanaeys in both places.

Table 5. Lexical similarities of Kankanaey in Rogus and Kankanaey in Cambaly.

VERBS

Kankanaey in Rogus and Kankanaey in Cambaly	
Find	<i>Anap</i> <i>Awag nu wada di naewed ay gamit yan adi maila.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Anapem isden kusina din inpayag ko ay taweng.</i>
Play	<i>Ay-ayam</i> <i>Am-amagen di anan-ak ya nataingan nu ewed di ubla da.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Man-ay-ayam tako si sungka.</i>
ADJECTIVES	
Glad	<i>Layad</i> <i>Karirikna nu wada di nailam ay am-ammom ay adin naila si nabayag.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Si lalayad nak ay makaila luman in sik-a. Kamusta ka ngay abo?</i>
Stink	<i>Agub</i> <i>Angot sin basura ay nabubulok yan adin naibbeng wennu baken mayat di angot na ay bagay.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Wada di man-agub issan kusina, ibbing yu kud din basura isdin likod di rwangan.</i>
Angry	<i>Bungot</i> <i>Karirikna nu wada di adin piyan di isa ay ipugao wennu wada di naamag ay adin nasiyaat.</i> <i>Haimbawa: Mabmabungot si Jeffrey en Allen tan kankanayon na gamin ay pantitripan.</i>
Cold	<i>Liteng</i> <i>Karirikna nu baken ay man-atung di panawen wennu makan o mainom.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Maliteng na ngarud di panawen nan, maliteng paylaeng san in-inomem.</i>
Attractive	<i>Kaay-ayo</i> <i>Awag nu wada di mapteng ay maila wennu ubla di isa ay kabsat.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Makaay-ayo iman din inamag na ay Christmas tree.</i>
Honest	<i>Pudno</i> <i>Awag sin ipugao ay baken man laslastog.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Pudno ay nginalat na sa, wada di ebidensiyak.</i>
Happy	<i>Radsak</i> <i>Awag sin karirikna nu wada di naimbag ay damage wennu naubla ay nagun-od di tarigagay.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Iyaman pay, naradsak nak para en sek-a si nagun-od mo egniman.</i>

Lexical Differences

Table 3.1 shows the categories of words that demonstrate lexical differences between Kankanaey Rogus and Kankanaey Cambaly. Findings show that lexical differences occur in verbs and adverbs. The Kankanaey word for cry in Rogus is *ibil*, and in Cambaly, it is *uga*. The word for clean in Rogus is *daus*, and in Cambaly *linis*. The word for sing in Rogus is *kansyon* and in Cambaly is *kanta*. The word for laugh in Rogus is *ammeng* and in Cambaly is *siyek*. The word for weave in Rogus is *abel*, and in Cambaly is *dait*.

Table 6. Lexical differences of Kankanaey in Rogus and Kankanaey in Cambaly.

VERBS		
	Kankanaey in Rogus	Kankanaey in Cambaly
Cry	<i>Ibil</i> <i>Karirikna di isa ay ipugao nu wada di adin nsiyaat ay pasamak kaman kuma nu wada di nateyan wennu din kankan da ay “tears of joy”</i> <i>Halimbawa: Nan-ibil sisya gapo iman tan nakapasa sis-ya sin exam da.</i>	<i>Uga</i> <i>Karirikna di isa ay ipugao nu wada di adin nsiyaat ay pasamak kaman kuma nu wada di nateyan wennu din kankan da ay “tears of joy”</i> <i>Halimbawa: Nan-uga sisya gapo tan taney din pusa na.</i>
Clean	<i>Daus</i>	<i>Linis</i>

	<i>Am-amagen nu wada di adin naurnos a gamit wennu naruot di arubayan.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Mandaus ka kud isdin likod di beey ad-ado di rugit isdi.</i>	<i>Am-amagen nu wada di adin naurnos a gamit wennu naruot di arubayan.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Linisam din kwartom tan nabayag ay ewed di na-ek isna.</i>
Laugh	<i>Ammeng</i> <i>Am-amagen nu wada di mayat ay damag wennu naradsak di isa ay ipugao.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Napipigsa di ammeng na ay basang sin buybuyaen da.</i>	<i>Siyek</i> <i>Am-amagen nu wada di mayat ay damag wennu naradsak di isa ay ipugao.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Nasiyek sisya sin naamwan na damag.</i>
Sing	<i>Kansyon</i> <i>Panagngalat ay am-amagen di ipugao ay wada di tuno na yan mabalin da ay ibirit.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Mayat iman di iyat da ay mankansyon adin mansakit si e-eng.</i>	<i>Kanta</i> <i>Panagngalat ay am-amagen di ipugao ay wada di tuno na yan mabalin da ay ibirit.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Sasa a di panagkanta kaman pankontes.</i>
Weave	<i>Abel</i> <i>Am-amagen di ipugao nu wada di napigis ay bado wennu man-amag si naduma дума ay gamit.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Man-ab-abel da iman si hambag ay ilako da.</i>	<i>Dait</i> <i>Am-amagen di ipugao nu wada di napigis ay bado wennu man-amag si naduma дума ay gamit.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Daitem kud gamin san badom ay napigis.</i>
ADVERBS		
	<i>Rogus</i>	<i>Cambali</i>
Fast	<i>Paspas</i> <i>Awag sin kaman managtag ay mandan.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Napaspas ka ah, nasangbot mo daida.</i>	<i>Partak</i> <i>Awag sin nasiglat ay man gungunay.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Napartak na ay nakdeng den am-amagen na.</i>
Hard	<i>Ligat</i> <i>Awag sin ewed di kakayahan na si biag, din maid nan-iskwela ya ewed di trabaho na ya beey na.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Naligat eman di ewed pelak na, ewed di maigatang si makan.</i>	<i>Rigat</i> <i>Karirikna no adin kabailan ay amagen din ubla.</i> <i>Halimbawa: Narigat ka abo ay ilaga.</i>

The table further shows only 2 differences. The word for hard in Rogus is *ligat* and in Cambaly is *rigat*. The word for fast in Rogus is *papas* and in Cambaly is *partak*. The foregoing findings confirm the fact that dialect shows lexical differences. This is related to what Hanks and Press (2013) highlighted in their study. They expressed that "the use of happen here meaning 'perhaps' or 'maybe' is an example of lexical variation - differences in vocabulary. It probably locates the speaker somewhere in an area centered on the Pennines: Yorkshire or Lancashire or adjacent areas of the East Midlands. The popular image of dialect speech tends to focus almost exclusively on dialect vocabulary and although there was at one time greater regional variation in vocabulary across the UK, there remains a great deal of lexical diversity".

Syntactical Similarities

Comparison in Syntax

This section shows the sentence structure of Kankanaey in Rogus.

1. I am going home.
(*Uuwi na ako sa bahay.*)

Figure 1. The Syntactic Structure of this sentence

The sentence on the left was constructed by a Kankanaey in Rogus. It is composed of one verb (sumaa) that is divided into one adjective (ak) one determiner (sin) and one noun (be-ey). The Syntactic Structure of this sentence is composed of a Verb phrase and a noun phrase.

The sentence on the right was constructed by a Kankanaey in Cambaly. The sentence shows that it is composed of one verb (sumaa-a) that is divided into one adjective (akon), one determiner (sin), and one noun (be-ey). The common Syntactic Structure of this sentence is composed of a Verb phrase and a noun phrase. Furthermore, both tree diagrams above show the same structure of the sentence in Rogus and Cambaly, they have a difference in the word they used the "sumaa-ak" and "sumaa-akon", but they are similar in the meaning. The word "sumaa" is "uuwi" in Tagalog or "going home" in English.

2. I will not cry anymore.
(*Hindi na ako iiyak kailanman.*)

Figure 2. The Syntactic Structure of this sentence

This sentence on the left was constructed by a Kankanaey in Rogus. It is composed of two adjectives (adi and ak) that are divided into one verb (man-ebelen) one determiner (si) and two adverbs (uray and kaanuman). The Syntactic Structure of this sentence is composed of a Verb phrase and two noun phrases.

The sentence above on the right was constructed by a Kankanaey in Cambaly. It is composed of two adjectives (adi and ak) that are divided into one verb (man-ug-uga) and one adverb (pay). The common Syntactic Structure or this sentence is composed of a Noun phrase and a Verb phrase.

The tree diagram shows the same structure of the sentence in Rogus and Cambaly. They have similarities in the word "man-ibilin" and "man-ug-uga" which represent the same verb. Just like in the previous sentences, the sentence structure is the same.

3. Jump high.
(Tumalon ng mataas.)

Figure 3. The Syntactic Structure of this sentence

The sentence on the left was constructed by a Kankanaey in Rogus. The said sentence shows that it is composed of one verb (Pimmadtok) that is divided into one determiner (si) and one adjective (sin). The Syntactic Structure of this sentence is composed of one Verb phrase and one noun phrase.

The sentence on the right was constructed by a Kankanaey in Cambaly. It is composed of one verb (Pimmadtok) that is divided into one pronoun (sis-ya) one determiner (si) and one adjective (nakayang). The Syntactic Structure of this sentence is composed of a Verb phrase and a noun phrase.

The tree diagram shows the same structure of the sentence in Rogus and Cambaly. They have similarities in sentence formation.

4. Jeffrey is working every day.
(Si Jeffrey ay nag tatabaho araw-araw.)

Figure 4. The Syntactic Structure of this sentence

The sentence on the left was constructed by a Kankanaey in Rogus. It is composed of one determiner (si) that is divided into one noun (Jeffrey) one verb (ay) one adjective (man-ub-ubla) one determiner (si) and one adjective (inagew). The Syntactic Structure of this sentence is composed of one phrase and two noun phrases.

The sentence of the right was constructed by a Kankanaey in Cambaly. It is composed of one adjective (Inag-agew) that is divided into one verb (ay) one adjective (man-ub-ubla) one determiner (si) and one noun (Jeffrey). The Syntactic Structure of this sentence is composed of a Verb phrase and two Noun phrases. The tree diagram shows the same structure of the sentence in Rogus and Cambaly. They have similarities in the formation of the sentence.

5. Beautiful morning.
(Magandang umaga)

Figure 5. The Syntactic Structure of this sentence

According to Casey Jergenson (2022), as you can probably tell at this point, Python is unique among these three languages, and Java and C++ are quite similar. When languages have similar syntax, this often means that they're based on an earlier language. Java and C++ are similar because both are based on the C programming language. This is another way in which programming languages are like human languages. Similarities in vocabulary, grammar, and syntax generally indicate a common ancestor. These similarities can be helpful when trying to learn a new language. If you're proficient in Java and you're trying to learn C++ or vice versa, you'll encounter some familiar elements that will streamline the process.

The sentence on the left was constructed by a Kankanaey in Rogus. It is composed of one adjective (Mapteng-ay) that is divided into one noun (agew). The Syntactic Structure of this sentence is composed of a Noun phrase.

This sentence on the left was constructed by a Kankanaey in Cambaly. It is composed of one adjective (Nasavaat-ay) that is divided into one noun (agew). The common Syntactic Sentence Structure of this sentence is composed of a Noun phrase.

The tree diagram shows the same structure of the sentence in Rogus and Cambaly. They have similarities in the word "Mapteng and Nasavaat," but they represent the same adjective, and in the structure of the sentence, they both express the same thought. As you can see, the word "ay" is only an expression in Kankanaey. It is like the "uhm" and "umm" in English. Furthermore, we found out that they don't have a difference when it comes to syntax. Instead, they have similarities.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to make a dialectal comparison in phonology, morphology, lexicon, and syntax. The phonological, morphological, lexical, and syntactic comparison provided the conclusion that there are similarities and differences in the features of the different components of language.

Phonological similarities and differences lie in the location of stress in certain words (noun, pronoun, and adverb/adjective). Morphological similarities are found in certain prefixes that are used to derive verbs and adverbs. Morphological differences are found in the prefixes that are attached to a certain verb. More specifically, the

differences are the initial sounds of the prefix. There are lexical similarities and differences also. There are words under the categories (verbs and adjectives) that are similar. There are words under the categories (verb and adverb) that are different. In terms of syntax, both the Kankanaey in Rogus and Cambaly are structurally the same.

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